

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D8.3 Guidance and recommendations for government and policy summary report

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Executive Summary

This report builds on the outcomes and insights of WP4, in order to develop guidance and recommendation for government responses, based on a critical review and cross-country analysis, lessons learned, and recommendations. D8.3 incorporates data from the desktop-research, residents' interviews, the expert interviews, and the case studies that take into account the lived experience of vulnerable residents. The guidance and recommendations will include: 1) a critical review of pandemic plans and 2) recommendations for protocols and principles for decision-makers taking the lead in implementing pandemic measures. The repertoire of lessons learned and guidance will be in a form that can help planners understand how different lessons from other regions might be applicable to them. The D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, focuses on the governmental responses towards COVID-19, based on a large desktop research conducted by the consortium partners among their fourteen respective countries. It summarized and assessed the responses per country, in terms of governmental structures, social, legal, cultural, and economic factors, that influence the governmental measures and responses towards COVID-19, and the adaptations to vulnerable groups as well media representation. The D4.2 Research design: Governmental responses, focused on the methodological development of research activities aimed at reviewing governmental structures and responses on a national level among the project target countries, as well as on a regional/local level in selected sub-national research sites and case studies, and by performing in parallel an in-depth analysis of key dimensions of governmental response impact in the project target countries. Specifically, the main objective was to specify the research questions and methods of primary data collection and analysis that would be utilized on the empirical research on governmental responses and the impacts these have on the target countries and to specific vulnerable populations. The D4.3 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment, focused on describing and assessing government response to the COVID-19 pandemic, in the following five dimensions: Pandemic planning and preparedness, Governmental approaches to defining and addressing vulnerability, Responses on multiple levels of governance, Economic and social welfare responses, Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors influencing government preparedness and response. Data, including those from previously published COVINFORM reports, complement and enriched primary data. The D4.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts, focused on the data drawn from the empirical and desktop research, by conducting an interpretation of the analysis between the governmental structure per country and adaptations for COVID-19: as of January 2020 until March 2021 and as of March 2021 until April 2022. It concluded with several recommendations based on the analysis of the available data. The D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – Update, as an update of the D4.1, focused on narrowing down the research, since the vast majority of the targeted countries adopted quite similar approaches in regard to governmental structures, laws and regulations, measures for vulnerable groups, crisis communication responses etc., and after presenting and comparing updates on governmental responses, attention was put on risk perceptions and vaccination initiatives and assessment. The D4.6 Research design: Governmental responses - update M26, was the second iteration of the methodological development in WP4. The D4.7 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment - update M32, as an update of the D4.3, focused on the following five dimensions of government response: Pandemic planning and preparedness, Economic and social welfare responses to COVID-19, COVID-19 responses on multiple levels of governance, Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors influencing government preparedness and response, Governmental approaches to defining and addressing vulnerability. In order to explore the government responses

overtime, the following time points were considered: T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic up until January 2020, T1: COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown until vaccination influenced measures, T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022. Finally, the D4.8 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts - update M33, focused on synthesizing data that is drawn from WP4 desktop and empirical research, with the synthesis of the governmental responses, impacts and subsequently the documentation of lessons learned, to be achieved by interpreting the analysis of governmental responses, structural alterations and studying the evolution of policies and practices. It has to be noted that throughout the Deliverables 4.1 to 4.8 there has been baseline and empirical research, with some of them being interconnected with each other.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease
D	Deliverable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EU	European Union
ICU	Intensive Care Unit
NPIs	Non-pharmaceutical interventions
UK	United Kingdom
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package
DGS	Directorate General of Health
ANPC	National Civil Protection Authority
PHA	Public Health Authority
CCS	Civil Contingencies Secretariat
NHS	National Health Service

1 Introduction

The beginning of 2020, was marked by the global health crisis of COVID-19 pandemic which impacted severely the wellbeing of society worldwide, bringing forward socioeconomic vulnerabilities, inequalities, and divisions among marginalised communities. The COVINFORM project's main objective was to capitalise on the multidisciplinary expertise of the sixteen consortium partners at all stages of the pandemic, and analyse and critique the COVID-19 responses on the levels of government, public health, community, and information and communications, developing at the same time risk assessment models, based on available quantitative data at the European level, leading towards the creation of an online portal and visual toolkit for governments, healthcare organizations, as well as citizens.

The main aim of the Work Package 4 (WP4): Government responses and impact assessment, was to emphasise on the governmental structures and responses, by reviewing them on a national level among the project target countries, as well as on a regional/local level in designated communities and case studies, performing in parallel an in-depth analysis of key dimensions of governmental response impact in the project target countries.

D4.1 aimed to gather and assess governmental responses, including a review of relevant primary sources (governmental policies and guidelines, official assessments and reports, etc.) and secondary sources discussing these governmental responses (scholarly studies, grey literature, etc.), thus resulting to a baseline concrete report with chapters per partner country, containing top-level descriptive analysis of relevant structures and responses. Special focus was given to vulnerable groups and the way those were affected (physically, economically, socially, and mentally) not only by COVID-19, but also mostly from the governmental response and reaction to it. D4.2 facilitated the development of the methodological aspect of the following deliverables by specifying the research questions and methods of primary data collection and analysis. Moreover, D4.3 aimed at providing an initial descriptive analysis and assessment of specific dimensions¹ of governmental responses and impacts in the EU and the COVINFORM target countries. D4.4 aimed to synthesize and interpret the findings of Deliverable 4.1 – Deliverable 4.3 from an interdisciplinary and intersectional perspective, within the theoretical framework established in WP2 and WP3 respectively. D4.5, an update on Deliverable 4.1, contained various results of the analysis of governmental structures and responses on the national level in fourteen of the target countries². D4.6 was an update on the guidance that is

¹ These specific dimensions are the following: Pandemic planning and preparedness, Governmental approaches to defining and addressing vulnerability, COVID-19 responses on multiple levels of governance, Economic and social welfare responses to COVID-19, Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors influencing government preparedness and response.

² D4.5 concluded in several observations such as: most countries adopted a central governmental approach issuing additional administrative powers to central points of authority such as Ministries instead of regional administrative entities. Furthermore, most countries identified vulnerabilities primarily based on health, economic, social factors, cultural, age as well as minority groups, single-parent families and business which were highly affected through the pandemic years, while for communication purposes, again multiple channels were utilized and most countries adopted a quite similar approach. Emphasis was put on vaccination initiatives and vaccination measures and procedures, risk perceptions as well as an overall update on governmental measures and structures.

necessary for the successful completion of Deliverable 4.7 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment - update M31 of the WP4 and, as such, it provided an overview as well as methodological reflections of the research conducted in WP4³. D4.7 aimed to provide an update of D4.3, “Analysis: Government Responses to COVID-19 and Impact Assessment,” which focused on describing and assessing government response to the COVID-19 pandemic, while D4.8 aimed to synthesize and interpret the findings of D4.5 – D4.7 from an interdisciplinary and intersectional perspective, within the theoretical framework established in WP2 and WP3, and it is structured by emphasizing on the synthesis and interpretation of findings which lead to the production of lessons learned and recommendations, which are intended to be utilized by governmental officials, decision makers and policy experts, academia and practitioners within the governmental mechanism⁴.

It is observed that throughout Deliverables 4.1 to 4.8, there has been baseline and empirical research, with some of those being interconnected with each other. Concluding, as it has been aforementioned and in accordance with the Grant Agreement of the COVINFORM project (Page 42 of 54), D8.3: Guidance and recommendations for government and policy summary report [36] provides an overview of the reports and other published materials and activities for government and policy. The main objective of D8.3 is to build on the outcomes and insights of WP4, in order to develop guidance and recommendation for government responses, based on a critical review and cross-country analysis, lessons learned, and recommendations. D8.3 incorporates data from the desktop-research, residents’ interviews, the expert interviews, and the case studies that take into account the lived experience of vulnerable residents. The guidance and recommendations will include: 1) a critical review of pandemic plans and 2) recommendations for protocols and principles for decision-makers taking the lead in implementing pandemic measures.

³ In the context of the WP4, the following main research questions are examined by all the COVINFORM consortium partners: What are the main milestones of the governmental responses adopted in each country during the different pandemic phases? In what ways have governmental measures been implemented and adapted across communities/populations, and have they been received? In what ways have governmental responses addressed specific vulnerabilities and inequalities across diverse communities/populations? What was the experience of vulnerable groups in relation to governmental response?

⁴ The overarching research questions which are examined in this Deliverable include the following: RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced? RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response? RQ3: What are the different kinds of barriers encountered in the pandemic response and how were they managed? RQ4: What are the main lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse social European environments?

2 Methodology

This deliverable is the outcome of the research conducted within the context of T8.2 Guidance and recommendations for government and policy, which builds on the outcomes and insights of WP4, develops guidance and recommendation for government responses, based on a critical review and cross-country analysis, lessons learned, and recommendations that include the data from the residents' interviews, the expert interviews, and the case studies to take into account the lived experience of vulnerable residents. This report includes: 1) a critical review of pandemic plans and 2) recommendations for protocols and principles for decision-makers taking the lead in implementing pandemic measures. According to the Grant Agreement (page 40 of 54), the repertoire of lessons learned and guidance will be presented in a form that can help planners understand how different lessons from other regions might be applicable to them. Partners involved in this task, have formulated the final scope of the task based on the stakeholder consultation and the findings from other tasks. The COVINFORM consortium has participated in several public events as part of the general agreement obligations to allow the project to disseminate early findings, engage stakeholders and get feedback to improve the content.

The primary aim of Work Package 4 (WP4: Government responses and impact assessment) was to describe and review governmental structures and responses among the project's target countries not only on a national level but on a regional/local level as well, in selected communities and case studies. In parallel an in-depth analysis of key dimensions of governmental responses impact is performed in relation to specific research questions and based on the reality of the targeted countries. Four tasks compose WP4 conducted in two iterations. T4.1 main objective was to pinpoint an overview of governmental structures and responses through desk-based research, T4.2 imprints the empirical research design, T4.3 focuses mainly on the empirical research, while T4.4 synthesizes research analysis and lessons learned across all tasks within the WP.

More in particular the deliverables under task 4.1 (D4.1, D4.5) aimed to describe and analyze the governmental structures, mechanisms and responses that have been deployed at the targeted countries since the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, comprising a baseline report that outlines identified commonalities and differences on a national and regional level and has been used as groundwork for further empirical research. The respective data collection pertains an overview of relevant primary sources including governmental policies and guidelines, official assessments and reports, produced directly by national governmental and policymaking bodies but also secondary sources (scholarly studies, grey literature, popular resources etc.) discussing the economic, health, social and mental impact of the implemented governmental policies and measures during the pandemic especially in relation to vulnerable groups.

For the aforementioned deliverable (D4.1) relevant entries covered the period from late January 2020 (as January is identified as the starting point of the pandemic in Europe) till end of March 2021 with a clear distinction between the different waves of the pandemic but also including entries from January 2019-January 2020 for purposes of comparison before and after the outbreak of the pandemic. For reasons of analytical cohesion while updating the baseline report (D4.5 – M 22 update) entries were requested to cover the period from April 1st 2021 till late May 2022. In addition to that, data relevant to risk perception and vaccination initiatives and procedures were also included since the main objective of this iteration of the deliverable has been to narrow down the research scope and shade

more light on how governmental responses were shaped and generated amidst the COVID 19 pandemic in the project target countries in order to produce a comparative analysis and discussion.

At both iterations of the deliverable the COVINFORM consortium partners who were involved in the respective task, received from the main Deliverable author KEMEA, corresponding guidebooks entailing analytical guidance, specific steps, requirements general objectives, data collection templates and procedures and standing deadlines as well.

The deliverables that report on task 4.2 *Conduct primary empirical research on governmental responses* outline the empirical research design conducted under WP4. More specific D 4.2 included the methodology scheme followed for the primary data collection on governmental responses and their impact on targeted countries in relation primarily with vulnerable population and results in producing D4.3. At that end, the aims, objectives and purposes of the research, the relevant guiding research questions, the sampling criteria, and target population, as well as the specific qualitative methods utilized for the study (semi-structured interviews,) were defined. Relevant indicators utilized in WP2 have been included in addition to project-level research questions established in WP3, but also baseline descriptive analyses per target country conducted in T4.1. Furthermore, the timeline for research activities, the foreseen research sites and the responsible partners as well as all the ethical and legal considerations that have been taken into account have also been outlined. In this context WP4-7 leaders have provided all partners with a shared Fieldwork manual that included all WP empirical research-specific sections and protocols (sampling, recruitment, topic guides), as well as a standardized information and consent sheet along with a standardized 'findings template'.

The second iteration of this deliverable (D4.6 -M26 update) which correlates with task 4.3 and subsequently produces D4.7 described the empirical research conducted within the framework of WP4 from late February 2022 until May 2023 in each target country. The aforementioned deliverable added on further to the previously conducted research by highlighting the observed differential consequences existing within regions and populations and underlining the COVID-19 pandemic impact the on vulnerable populations. In addition, emphasis was placed on identifying the way governmental responses were affected and shaped amidst the pandemic and because of it, especially in relation to the pre-existing crisis management plan/mechanisms.

Both deliverables D4.3 and its correlating update D4.7, that report under task 4.3, drew upon the findings of the desktop research reported in D4.1 and in the subsequent D4.5 –M22 update and explore further the reasoning behind the adoption of a specific response in each target country as the pandemic evolved through the different phases. The empirical research which officially initiated in mid-October 2021 has been carried out in ten local sub-national geographically defined research sites in partner countries, selected by site-appropriate quantitative and/or qualitative indicators of vulnerability criteria in the context of the pandemic. The population of interest has been governmental actors, public authorities, and policy makers (e.g., Ministries of Health, of Citizens Protection, and generally with decision making powers during the pandemic) at a desired size sample of $N \geq 5$ while the main qualitative method followed has been semi-structured interviews.

D4.7 provided an update of the initial findings presented in D4.3 report utilizing also data from the updated baseline D4.5 deliverables and the expert interviews conducted within WP4 framework. Although most of the countries finalized their interviews by May 2023 further interviews have been conducted prior to D4.7 analyses for those COVINFORM partners that did not secure the required sample (n, 5) by February 2022 due to recruitment challenges caused by the course of the pandemic

and the key role of the targeted experts in its management. In this context WP Leader KEMEA designed a strategy to mitigate the risk of potential data acquisition challenges providing the option to conduct additional qualitative, quantitative and /or desktop research to supplement partners' contribution especially for those challenged by relevant data inadequacy.

As the primary goal of this update focused on exploring temporality and change relevant to governmental responses in the course of the pandemic, the conducted analysis has taken into consideration three different phases of the pandemic, based upon Ostrom's SES framework:

- T0: Baseline pre COVID-19 pandemic up until January 2020
- T1: COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures
- T2: Omicron from November 2021 up until September 2022).

Prior to the analysis the acquired data were assigned to the WP4 relevant research dimensions in order to identify, group together and compare existing commonalities between partner countries. At that end, the aforementioned report contains not only information from previous deliverables but also updated information and new data to some extent.

The main objective of the analysis conducted under the task T4.4 which resulted in D4.4 and its update (D 4.8. -M33) was to synthesize the impact of governmental responses, policies and practices during the COVID-19 pandemic but also to document and explore lessons learned and recommendations that can potentially be used to equal or similar scale future healthcare crisis.

D4.4 focused mainly on synthesizing data drowned from WP4 desktop and empirical research, emphasizing on documenting the main findings and lessons learned stemming from previous data collection specifically in relation to D4.1 and D4.3. A descriptive analysis of governmental structures, responses, policies, practices and their adaptations in the targeted countries between January 2020 and April 2022 was subsequently produced. At that end, the second iteration of this deliverable (D 4.8. -M33) includes an in-depth presentation of cross country comparative analysis of the different governmental structures and the changes that occurred between April 2022 until July 2023, exploring further the analysis conducted in D4.7 but also utilizing research findings stemming from D4.5 and D4.6 which also serve as a basis for the synthesis and lessons learned on governmental responses and impacts in the era of COVID 19.

The main scope of the D4.8 - M33 update has been, not only identify and document good practices and policies relating to the governmental response mechanism and the pandemic management of COVID-19 but also essentially proceed to the production of specific recommendations for all relevant stakeholders with an active role in governmental response mechanisms against the COVID-19, such as governmental officials and decision makers, practitioners and academics on European, national, regional and local scope. To achieve that in a more concrete way, a methodological change of course has been introduced in D4.8 by incorporating the same methodological framework used in D4.7 meaning the thorough examination and presentation of three distinct pandemic phases:

- Model T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
- Model T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination
- Model T2: Post-vaccination

The research emphasized on three thematic areas:

- Governmental responses and preparedness

- Changes on policies and practices
- Vulnerability

Therefore, conducting a more integrated analysis and methodological approach.

2.1 WP4 Empirical Research Framework

The empirical research conducted within WP4 aimed mainly to capitalize the findings from the desktop research executed under task 4.1. Although these findings provided an adequate overview of the governmental policies implemented in the targeted countries in order to manage the effects of the pandemic, the need to explore further the reasoning behind the adaptation of these governmental responses emerged emphatically. At that end specific research was executed within 10 of the 15 target sub-national/ sub-municipal units (region, urban neighborhood, rural village, etc.), in order to produce an in-depth analysis highlighting the social, economic, health, mental and general impact governmental responses had on the relevant research sites, how they have been accepted and their consequences if any on the levels of trust towards governmental actors and policy makers. The aforementioned subnational research sites have been chosen as per Table 1 below.

Table 1. Overview of the research sites included in the present report

Partner	Country	Sub-national site
SYNYO	Austria	Vienna
UANTWERPEN	Belgium	Antwerpen
KEMEA	Greece	Athens
SAPIENZA, UCSC	Italy	Rome
FS	Portugal	Évora
SNCRR	Romania	Babadag
URJC, SAMUR	Spain	Madrid
UGOT	Sweden	Gothenburg
TRI, MDI	England	Birmingham
SU	Wales	Swansea

2.2 Sampling criteria and target population

The objective of the empirical research across all WPs4-7 has been to include citizens/community members' perspectives in their respective analysis. This group is accessed as a 'shared' sample which has been split between the work packages, in such a way that citizens/community members participate equally in the research centered around the main thematic areas of WP4. At that end, WP4 the main population of interest has been Governmental actors, public authorities, and policy makers (e.g., Ministries of Health, of Citizens Protection, and generally with decision making powers during the

pandemic) at a desired number of $N \geq 5$ representatives. More in particular each involved partner has been asked to include at least: $N \geq 3$ representatives from the respective Ministry of Citizens Protection or the Ministry/authority responsible for shaping the main policies towards COVID-19 pandemic and being also in charge of the relevant communication strategy and $N \geq 2$ representatives from the respective Ministry of Health and from the respective authorities responsible for the Vaccination initiatives in each targeted country.

Participants were identified and recruited through snowball (expert purposive) sampling, based on the professional networks and contacts stemming from the consortium partners. The utilized purposive sampling methodology was considered to best enable researchers to address the specific research questions of interest since participants with specific expertise even though are the desirable ones to be sharing their knowledge on the studied subject it is firmly acknowledged that the specific sample cannot be representative of the general population under study.

2.3 Research methodology

As the overarching research questions of the COVINFORM project have been RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?, RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?, RQ3: What were the lived experiences of the pandemic and its response of certain vulnerable groups?, RQ4: What were the different kinds of barriers encountered in the pandemic response and how were they managed?, RQ5: What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?, the methodology that was utilized as the most appropriate to address research questions within the context of WP4 “Government responses and impact assessment”, has been the qualitative approach. Qualitative research conducted under WP4 mainly aims in providing an in-depth examination and analysis of the pandemic as a multi-dimensional phenomenon, emphasizing on exploring the complexity of governmental responses, the way these evolved during the pandemic. At that end, empirical research in WP4 consisted of two main activities: work package –specific expert interviews with governmental actors, public authorities and policy makers as specified in the above 2.1 section and resident interviews with low socio-economic status (SES) women as an apportioned empirical research scheme between WP4-7. A shared Fieldwork manual including all WP-specific sections (sampling, recruitment, topic guides) as well as standardized information and consent sheet, along with a standardized 'findings template' for each WP in which research partners can report their findings in English has been formed and distributed by WP4-7 leaders.

2.4 Semi-structured interviews

The research method for this study was chosen under the concept of phenomenological interviewing. This type of interviewing is established under the philosophical paradigm of phenomenology, which is based on the perception that people’s lived experiences shape their world view. The interviews will be formatted in a semi-structured manner. They are chosen as a method as they are essential in one-on-one discussions that include the examination of “how” and “why” something happens (political decisions, laws, guidelines etc.). They are also optimal when interviewing service providers and administration actors, with whom further follow-up questions might be necessary. Moreover, semi-structured interviews are best suited for discussions with state actors and political personnel, since they provide space for narrations and storytelling that have to do with decision-making, motivation, and behaviour. Finally, since the goal of the research is to delve deeper to the why’s and how’s related to the governmental responses towards COVID-19 pandemic, based on the experiences and opinions of the actors involved in them, one cannot limit the questions to a questionnaire but rather opt for semi-structured discussions where other topics or subcategories of relevance might come up.

2.5 Cross-Work Package empirical research

The second round of empirical research was conducted from June to September 2022, during which N=12 low-socioeconomic-status (SES) women were interviewed per target site (total N=120). The inclusion criteria for potential participants were: 1) female self-identification; and 2) self-identification as a recipient of financial or material support from social welfare programmes or civil society organisations. Women who would be eligible to receive support based on their financial circumstances, but were excluded due to nationality, residence status, or other extra-economic factors (e.g., inability to navigate bureaucratic barriers, etc.) were also invited to participate. The decision to focus on low-SES women was taken for several reasons:

- Low SES has been consistently identified as a risk factor for adverse outcomes not only in the economic domain, but also the health and social domains; likewise, gender was identified early on as a mediating factor in experiences of the pandemic. This is true across national contexts, making cross-national comparative analysis appropriate.
- Choosing a narrowly defined target population enabled data saturation with a comparatively small within-country sample of N=12. With regard to sample size, a balance needed to be struck between suitability for within-county vs. cross-country analysis. On the one hand, the sample per country needed to be large enough to yield meaningful findings on the target population within the target site; on the other hand, interviewing a very large sample per country would generate too large of a cross-national dataset to be comprehensively analysed within the project timeframe.
- Choosing a narrowly defined target population is also beneficial from the standpoint of actionability. Particular policies and measures are designed to support low-SES women, and particular institutions serve them. Findings on low-SES women's experiences of the pandemic are directly relevant to the stakeholders involved.
- Throughout the project, consideration was given to both 'ascribed vulnerability' (being labelled as vulnerable by others or institutions) and the 'lived experience of vulnerability' – as well as to differences in the ways vulnerability is described from emic and etic perspectives. Focusing on a target population widely perceived as vulnerable provides the opportunity to delve into such differences.
- None of the WP3 case studies focused on this target population (though many of the case study target populations overlapped with it).

An interview topic guide was created collaboratively by the WP4, WP5, WP6, and WP7 teams, which encompassed project-level research questions and a selection of sub-questions critical to each WP. The topic guide was influenced by the model of the problem-centred interview (PCI), a theory-driven model of semi-structured interview intended to enable the research participant to describe their way of making sense of a given 'problem' without being unduly influenced by the researcher and her theoretical concept (Mohr 1998; Witzel 2012). In keeping with the PCI model, the topic guide began with a broad question designed to elicit an open narration: "Could you tell me about when you first realised that the COVID-19 pandemic would affect your everyday life?" Interviewers were instructed not to interrupt interviewees, but rather to wait for a natural break before introducing the second

question, which was also narrative: “When you think back, could you tell me the three most important memories of the COVID-19 pandemic?” In order to ensure that sufficient data was collected on topics relevant to WP4-7, this opening narrative block was followed by a block of traditional semi-structured interview questions on the topics of social networks and support, information-seeking and sense-making, and living environments. A focus on social networks and relationships was taken because socioeconomic disadvantage often leads to social exclusion, which can in turn limit access to information or instrumental forms of support. During the pandemic, lockdown and social distancing measures aggravated the isolation of some individuals, despite more social support being needed to cope with the stress factors surrounding finances, health, and wellbeing. It was hypothesised that low-SES women were ‘double burdened’ during the pandemic, facing greater vulnerability to the negative impacts of COVID-19 and COVID-19 response measures alike.

Recruiting was conducted through gatekeeper organisations. In some cases, participants were recruited directly through the organisations that provided them with financial or material support. In other cases (e.g., when social welfare institution policies did not permit such cooperation), recruiting was conducted via other civil society organisations that serve vulnerable women, using a screener. Gatekeepers were not coerced, manipulated, or unduly induced financially or otherwise to assist with recruiting.

Careful consideration was given as to how to compensate participants for any expenses they incurred, and/or for their time and intellectual labour (Fry and Dwyer 2001; Head 2009; Russell et al. 2000; Singer and Kulka 2002). This required balancing the potential of “undue inducements” to compromise the voluntariness of consent and the reliability of the data collected (European Commission Directorate-General for Research 2010, p. 38-39) against the fact that economic precarity can “[exclude certain groups] from participation in research” (ibid., p. 121). It also required acknowledging the privilege of the researcher, who is materially compensated for their own participation in the “knowledge co-production” (Fedyuk and Zentai 2018). Due to institutional constraints on some partners, the decision as to whether or not to offer financial honoraria or comparable incentives (e.g., vouchers) was made on a partner-by-partner basis. Those partners that did offer honoraria, did so in a confidential and safe manner, making it clear that they were unconditional.⁵ A further effort taken to increase inclusivity was active outreach to potential participants that faced access barriers that might normally prevent their voices from being heard: e.g., age, physical disabilities, etc.

In accordance with the COVINFORM ethics framework, a comprehensive project information sheet in simple language was provided, and potential participants were given the opportunity to ask questions about the project and the interview procedure before being asked to sign an informed consent form. Participants were given the option of conducting their interview either face-to-face or via telephone

⁵ The use of monetary incentives in medical and psychological research, including public health research, has long been a matter of convention (Russell, Moralejo & Burgess 2000). Their use in sociological and anthropological research is less common, and has been viewed by some researchers as methodologically questionable (ISA 2001, in Head 2009, 340). However, among qualitative researchers working in feminist scholarly traditions, “omitting to pay participants has sometimes been characterised as unethical, so that making payments (or gift-giving) becomes a mark of ethically sound research” (Head 2009, 337). In light of these considerations, the COVINFORM consortium determines that reasonable “fair returns for assistance” are methodologically justifiable as a means of reducing possible socioeconomic barriers to participation, thereby helping to mitigate the risk of implicitly “[excluding certain groups] from participation in research and the benefits that may attach to research participation” (European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation 2010, p. 121).

or online. The interviews were recorded and transcribed by the interviewing partners; the transcripts were then pseudonymised, translated into English, and shared with the consortium via a secure folder. Coding was conducted by the WP leaders – KEMEA, UANTWERPEN, SINUS, and SYNYO – using a collaboratively-designed codebook in the software package MAXQDA.

3 Analysis, cross-country comparison and critical review of preparedness - pandemic plans

According to deliverable D5.7 Analysis: Public health responses and impact - update M33 and D4.7 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment – update M32, which provide an overview of how the COVID-19 pandemic was managed in terms of public health responses and governmental responses, including changes over time, by the 10 COVINFORM states (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, England, Wales), also reveals how the pre-pandemic plans in Europe were utilized. Beginning with Austria, the pre-pandemic plans of each of the 10 European countries will be presented.

Austria did not have a holistic pandemic plan, before the COVID-19 pandemic. Austria had a National [Influenza Plan](#) from 2006⁶, which was considered outdated and not been updated since 2006, therefore was considered not suitable for the COVID-19 pandemic. While the vulnerable groups were only included in a generic way in the aforementioned National Influenza Plan. The only instrument which was in force during the COVID-19 pandemic was the old Austrian Epidemic Act 1950, which did not undergo any major changes since its emergence. The first package of measures introduced by the Austrian government was released on March 15, 2023, which included the first lockdown, and it was the COVID-19 Act.

Belgium prior to COVID-19 outbreak, all pandemic preparedness was the responsibility of federal government actors and the Sciensano public health institute. Belgium had a National Pandemic [Influenza Plan from 2006](#)⁷ that emphasized tailored communication strategies for different audiences, yet the plan lacked specificity on vulnerable populations, recovery, and evaluation of mitigation measures, despite that an advisory report was issued in 2009 regarding the 2006 plan.

Germany had the First, Second, and Third Acts on the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance, to assign powers to the relevant authorities that were in accordance with the broad provisions of the 2001 Protection against Infection Act, [Influenza Pandemic Preparedness Plan](#)⁸ and the 2017 National Pandemic Plan. The Second Act furthermore consisted of provisions that improved preventative testing under the statutory health insurance system (SHI), improved working conditions for HCWs, especially those involved in geriatric care, improved communications between the Robert Koch Institute and public health services, and improved flexibility and reduced bureaucracy within the insurance system, for the insured and healthcare providers alike. The National Pandemic Plan was updated by the Robert Koch Institute on the 4th of March 2020, entailing recommendations specific to each of the three stages in a pandemic management: A) “Containment” phase: which enhanced the early detection, intensified focus on society-wide and targeted testing, and introduced contact tracing apps (with adequate data protection and accompanying user sensitisation). B) “Protection” phase: which considered, hard lockdowns and other social distancing measures stricter than previously anticipated, and the importance of mask-wearing and ventilation. C) “Mitigation” phase: which anticipated the need for variant surveillance; redoubled

⁶ <https://docplayer.org/74915129-Influenza-pandemieplan-strategie-fuer-oesterreich.html>.

⁷ <https://extranet.who.int/sph/influenza-plan-belgium>.

⁸ https://www.rki.de/EN/Content/infections/epidemiology/inf_dis_Germany/influenza/influenza_germany/Report_Influenza.html.

focus on vaccine development, including anticipated need for booster vaccines; consideration of novel (pharmaceutical) treatment approaches; and intensified focus on adaptive public health communication. On 14 December 2021, the Federal Government broadened the scope of pandemic planning by convening a Coronavirus Expert Council (Corona ExpertInnenrat der Bundesregierung).

Greece did not have its structure of the healthcare system radically change, in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Greece based its response utilizing the [2009 National Action Plan toward the Influenza Pandemic](#)⁹. The National Public Health Organization (EODY), a public healthcare organization, supervised by the Ministry of Health which also had and continues to have a central role in the healthcare system, closely monitored the COVID-19 pandemic and established frequent and sustainable communication with both the WHO and the European Center for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC).

Italy since the end of 2003, when the outbreaks of avian influenza by virus became endemic in birds and the virus caused infections in humans as well, the risk of an influenza pandemic had been more concrete and persistent. For this reason, that then the WHO recommended all countries to develop a Pandemic Plan and to constantly update it following agreed lines. The “[Piano nazionale di preparazione e risposta a una pandemia influenzale](#)” [National influenza pandemic preparedness and response plan, 2006]¹⁰ was drawn up according to the 2005 WHO guidelines, which updated and replaced the previous Italian Multiphase Plan for and Influenza Pandemic, published in 2002. However, the Ministerial Circular “New Coronavirus Pneumonia (2019-nCov) China” of 22 January 2020 was officially declared to address the first cases COVID-19 in Italy.

Portugal had a crisis communication framework in place, which comprised a national emergency plan and a communication strategy. While Direção-Geral da Saúde/DGS supervised the communication of health-related information to the public and healthcare rules, the National Civil Protection Authority (ANPC) oversee, coordinated and communicated emergency responses. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the DGS worked closely with other government departments, particularly the Ministry of Health, to organise the national response to the pandemic, conducting thorough and lengthy investigation but was unable to uncover any earlier COVID-19 crisis-related government communication plans or initiatives. The Portuguese government had documentations in place before and during the COVID-19 pandemic to cope with pandemics and other crisis circumstances; for example, the [National Plan for Pandemic Influenza](#) (2007)¹¹ and the National Emergency Plan, but the pandemic highlighted gaps in these plans, including the need for more resources, coordination among different sectors, and flexibility in adapting to new situations.

Spain managed the initial pandemic response under the [National Influenza Response Plan](#)¹², which was not designed for a pandemic with similar features. This led to logistical and organisational challenges, due to a limited legal and operational framework., and as the pandemic's scale became apparent, there was a need to develop a tailored legal framework and streamline administrative procedures for rapid mobilisation of resources. This included hiring more professionals, expanding inventory of protective equipment and medicines, but the absence of a pandemic-specific plan, had a detrimental impact on the timely, coordinated, and effective response of professionals and public administrations,

⁹ <https://extranet.who.int/sph/influenza-plan-greece>.

¹⁰ <https://www.salute.gov.it/portale/influenza/dettaglioPubblicazioniInfluenza.jsp?lingua=italiano&id=501>.

¹¹ <https://extranet.who.int/sph/influenza-plan-portugal>.

¹² <https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/docs/PlanGripeIngles.pdf>.

occasionally overwhelming health and social services. In July 2020 that the Early Response Plan in a scenario of COVID-19 pandemic control was presented.

Sweden commissioned the NBHW in 2005 to produce a [national pandemic plan](#) that included plans for national interventions and provided a basis for regional planning¹³. The plan was revised in 2009, and later in 2012 after the swine flu, and again in 2015 after the Ebola outbreak¹⁴. Since 2015, the PHA (The Public Health Agency of Sweden) coordinates pandemic preparedness at national level in Sweden, providing support for planning at regional and local levels. The pandemic plan was revised again in 2019. The current plan consists of three volumes: A) How we prepare – a knowledge-base. B) How we communicate – a knowledge-base. C) Pandemic preparedness. Access to and use of pharmaceuticals – guidelines. The overall structure of the Swedish crisis management system was that in an eventful crisis the handling by public authorities should occur according to their respective areas of responsibility, following the three basic principles of responsibility, equality, and proximity. The Government's tasks in crisis management involved primarily strategic issues, and the responsibility for command and coordination of operational work rested with the relevant authorities and agencies, such as the PHA, the Swedish Civil Contingency Agency's (SCCA) and the 21 national County Administrative Boards. Finally, most Swedish hospitals had a pandemic plan prior to the COVID-19 outbreak, but their scope and focus varied widely.

England had three pandemic plans, that existed before the COVID-19 pandemic. They are the following: 1) UK Influenza Contingency Plan (2005). 2) National Framework for responding to an influenza pandemic (2007). 3) UK [Influenza Pandemic Preparedness Strategy](#) (2011)¹⁵. England had previously engaged in pandemic exercises to evaluate the entire UK's preparedness and response to a flu pandemic, with those exercises focusing on a flu pandemic, including the Cygnet and Cygnus (2016) and the Pica (2018). These plans were never published and were not disclosed to parliament. However, the NHS stepped into the COVID-19 pandemic in a more strenuous position compared to other health systems, due to a decade of underfunding.

Wales had its pre-pandemic preparedness strategy aligned to the overarching UK-wide strategy, with the main Welsh document resembling a pandemic response plan or strategy, being the [Wales Framework for Managing Infectious Disease Emergencies 2005](#).¹⁶ It "sets out national arrangements for managing major infectious disease emergencies, including national coordination, operational responsibilities of NHS organisations, as well as the role of partner agencies" (ibid). Wales also had a more pandemic-specific response plan; the 2007 Pandemic Influenza Guidance Planning, which was established before the 2009 influenza pandemic. For emergencies in general, Wales has the [Pan-Wales Response Plan](#)¹⁷, which entails the "command, control and coordination of urgent response structure for national emergencies and includes activation levels and multi-agency responsibilities" (ibid). On the 18th of March 2020, Wales initiated its own health protection regulations, the Coronavirus Restrictions that were approved by the Welsh Parliament on March 25th, giving its authorities the power to manage the pandemic independently of the other British nations.

¹³ <https://www.socialstyrelsen.se/globalassets/sharepoint-dokument/artikelkatalog/ovrigt/2012-12-7.pdf>.

¹⁴ <https://extranet.who.int/sph/influenza-plan-sweden>.

¹⁵ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/213717/dh_131040.pdf.

¹⁶ <https://covid19.public-inquiry.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/21174018/INQ000183456.pdf>.

¹⁷ <https://covid19.public-inquiry.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/21175547/INQ000089571.pdf>.

Overall it is concluded that the majority of target states such as: Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, England and Wales were able to utilize pre-existing pandemic preparedness plans, as these states developed Influenza pandemic plans prior to COVID-19. Contrary to the majority of target states, only a minority of countries developed a holistic pandemic preparedness plan, which could be utilized for all potential healthcare risks of a pandemic scale, such as Wales and Sweden. Concluding, COVID-19 was an unprecedented phenomenon, thus, in order to combat this pandemic effective and efficiently, even though some states had a holistic preparedness plan while some other target countries relied mainly on influenza plans, all target states are observed to conduct a series of governmental interventions on crisis management systems, changes in healthcare systems and adopted additional measures via legislative acts.

4 Analysis and cross-country comparison of governmental responses: low Socio-Economic Status resident interviews

This section conducts an in-depth analysis and a cross-country comparison of the research findings that relate to governmental responses and crisis management towards COVID-19. The data is based on 12 per target country low socio-economic status resident interviews. Moreover, this section focuses on two thematic areas:

- 1) Governmental responses, crisis management and critique
- 2) Desired support and vulnerability

In **Austria**, interviewees similarly to all target countries have had negative experiences from the lockdown and social distancing protocols, as well as with the mandatory masks and vaccinations. Similarly, to other countries, these policies have caused socio-economic and interpersonal damage as an indirect consequence of their implementation, nevertheless interviewees appear conflicted, similarly to Sweden, on what else could have been done differently and if other options were available from the crisis management standpoint. In Austria, in several cases interviewees were entitled to benefits in order to compensate the negative financial impact from COVID-19 policies, however, these are considered to be insufficient, while some interviewees report bureaucratic issues with their legal documentation which lead to their exclusion from receiving any governmental assistance. Concluding, similarly to several other target countries, interviewees indicate that some politicians should be held accountable for not abiding to the implemented measures during COVID-19 and highlights that there is an issue of trust. In relation to desired support, interviewees strongly believe that politicians should be held accountable and ought to be an example for other citizens. Interviewees would also prefer to have a better welfare state, particularly for low socio-economic status citizens and the elderly, who in many cases were deprived of essential need items, similarly to most countries. In addition, one interviewee suggested the need of implementing rules in an indiscriminately, particularly with the mandatory quarantine from travelers who come from abroad. Concluding, interviewees appear divided on the role of decision makers, indicating to have felt betrayed by the government, while others suggest that they are content with the management of the crisis by the government. In sum, interviewees desire the implementation of clear rules during a crisis and better degree of welfare support. In relation to vulnerability, interviewees indicate that COVID-19 and the relevant policies had a significant negative impact in their psychological wellbeing, thus, sought coping mechanisms. Vulnerability in Austria was exuberated on all target groups, but was particularly apparent in low socio-economic status groups as well as the elderly.

In relation to governmental responses and criticism in **Belgium**, most interviewees indicate that governmental initiatives were lacking such as the placement of many rules led to the exclusion of citizens in receiving benefits during the crisis. Citizens appear to be challenged mainly by movement restrictions, lack or insufficient communication, abrupt cease of employment, digitization of services and employment whereas and at a lesser rate wearing masks. Moreover, albeit some citizens appear to criticize the governmental responses, some interviewees have a more neutral point of view. In all cases, COVID-19 influenced citizens particularly negatively on psychological terms. Emotional challenges were exuberated and cases of chronic depression would be intensified. Interviewees suggest that in some cases financial support was sufficient while others suggest too many rules may exclude beneficiaries. A common finding is the severely negative impact that movement restrictions

and distance protocols had on society, particularly on children. In relation to desired support, interviewees would like to receive a higher degree of financial and psychological support, witness governmental pro-activeness through initiatives, clear communication and oversee market trends while regulating prices, as household expenses were elevated during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In **England**, the main challenge and criticism regarding governmental responses are observed to be the lack of substantial economic support and the negative psychological impact from the lack of human face to face interactions due to the movement containment measures. One interviewee indicates that the abrupt changes brought by COVID-19, were to a certain point mitigated by governmental response. Adjustment to the new working modus operandi was challenging for some interviewees while also experienced practical challenges. All interviewees appear to be in consensus regarding the negative impact of responses leading to lack of physical and social interaction. According an interviewee, the impact of movement restriction responses influenced their daily habits on a long-term period. In relation to governmental, particularly psychological support, one interviewee suggested that their family was sufficient and did not seek professional support, while another indicated that governmental support did not exist. Interviewees also criticized governmental behavior which negatively impacted their trust during COVID-19 restrictions. In relation to desired support, interviewees suggest they would like to be offered more psychological support, acts of solidarity and human interaction. In terms of information, most interviewees suggest that the governmental website would provide the most on point information, nevertheless, they have experienced an overload of information which can be negative. Concluding, besides social isolation which influences negatively citizens, in certain cases, the measure of wearing masks can be challenging for individuals with physical vulnerabilities such as hearing issues.

In **Germany** interviewees similarly to other countries criticize governmental responses particularly in relation to social isolation and movement containment policies, as well as highlight cases in which social distancing did not apply to politicians, which caused criticism. Moreover, interviewees appear to be critical of the governmental crisis management mechanism, suggesting that decision makers fail to research thoroughly COVID-19 and taken action too late. In terms of support, respondents appear divided as some have claimed benefits while others were excluded as beneficiaries or deem the received support as insufficient. Another point of criticism for respondents, similarly to most target states is the lack of welfare support, employment protection and provision of healthcare in terms of psychological wellbeing. Similarly, to other countries, in Germany COVID-19 had a significantly negative impact on all aspects of life for citizens. In relation to desired support, German interviewees indicate the need of equipment provision for homeschooled children, welfare support for the general public as well as low socio-economic citizens and the elderly. Moreover, interviewees highlight the need to have clear and understandable crisis communication, as well as better socio-economic support for citizens that were negatively impacted from COVID-19. In addition, interviewees suggest that policy experts and decision makers ought to be more proactive, knowledgeable about the crisis at hand, respect individual liberties and also take into account the negative socio-psychological impact that containment policies can have on the wellbeing of children and vulnerable groups. Further, citizens indicate the need for a market regulation authority to protect low socio-economic citizens, as prices have significantly been increased, whilst underline the need for governmental responses to also emphasize in securing the provision of essential need items. In terms of vulnerability, interviewees in Germany, similarly to other countries suggest that children and the elderly have been negatively impacted significantly, as well as low socio-economic status citizens, who experienced depression as

an indirect consequence of COVID-19 and the relevant policies. Citizens indicate the need for an increased welfare support for the most vulnerable citizens.

In **Greece**, all participants expressed a negative opinion of the governmental responses, particularly during the first phase, while in some cases interviewees suggested that there was a complete absence of governmental support for their families, a situation that they are accustomed even prior to the pandemic. The impact and negative consequences of COVID-19 and governmental responses was experienced in the early phases of the pandemic from both socio-economical and health perspective. In sum, citizens criticized the effectiveness of responses, indicated challenges to make meets end, highlighted the need to make the welfare system more encompassing and underlined the inadequately of governmental support. Another main finding is that several participants would criticize governmental measures that would hinder the opportunities of securing a stable employment status during COVID-19, highlight challenges to ensure their social and financial survival as well as the perceived negative impact by the implemented movement restriction policies. Another main finding of the governmental responses and implemented measures is the severe consequences and impact on the wellbeing of low socio-economic citizens, particularly of single-parent families, that struggle on a daily basis and are simultaneously impacted by the lack of substantial welfare assistance. The socially “translucent” state that low SES citizens, particularly single-parent families, is observed to be a long-term socio-economic issue in the Greek society, which verifies the fact that the pandemic has exuberated systemic weaknesses and socio-economic vulnerabilities. According to respondents, the criteria to secure a financial benefit are perceived to be very strict, therefore many citizens in dire need are left out of the support process. This finding is particularly important and decision makers as well as policy experts should take it into consideration during the re-evaluation of welfare policies process. In accordance with the aforementioned findings and testimonies, it would be safe to conclude that in relation to low SES citizens in Greece, governmental responses towards COVID-19 had a negative direct and indirect impact in their daily lives, while a lack of substantial support towards single-parent families is observed, a phenomenon that pre-existed COVID-19. In relation to governmental support towards low socio-economic status citizens is the perceived lack and desired support on a local level via information dissemination and community engagement, particularly at a municipal level. It is observed that community engagement, particularly from municipalities is severely underdeveloped. According to respondents, albeit in some cases Municipalities have engaged to a certain degree, community interactions have mostly been underwhelming and ineffective, as widespread fear and insecurity due to the lack of guidance ensued at a long-term basis. Participants suggest that they would prefer governmental support via tailored initiatives, transparent information dissemination and engagement at a municipal level. Moreover, indicate that that bureaucratic challenges may exclude beneficiaries from the acquisition of valuable support, whereas a substitute approach is required to overcome systemic weaknesses. Another main finding, relevant to governmental support is the high number of interviewees that did not receive welfare, in the form of emergency benefit to mitigate the suspension of employment and ensure their survivability. In cases that such support was provided, it was due to certain rules and conditions, which were considered ineffective and posed challenges, therefore several vulnerable citizens would be excluded due to bureaucratic issues. This system gap is observed to be filled by CSOs such as the NGO Aggalia, which according to respondents has a significant part in their wellbeing with the provision of essential need items and support. In particular, participants are observed to suggest the significance of CSOs’ support, as a substitute entity offering support, in face of the absence or inadequacy of governmental support in both services and materialistic products. In Greece, similarly to all of the target countries, it is apparent that that vulnerability is a

multidimensional phenomenon, which may include socio-economic, legal, cultural and health factors. Moreover, it is certain that COVID-19 has exuberated pre-existing vulnerabilities which were intensified by systemic weaknesses, and created new vulnerabilities that relate to the consequences of the COVID-19 policies. The absence of a protective mechanism for low socio-economic status citizens, particularly in securing accommodation through the pandemic is an important issue, as many individuals would not continue to be employed due to governmental policies, and insufficient mitigation measures. Concluding the lack of welfare protocols may increase the vulnerabilities of low SES citizens, movement restriction policies can lead to severe unintended outcomes such as mental and physical health deterioration. The social vulnerability of low SES citizens was intensified also due to the radical change of societal interactions, even with individuals to their close environment, which was part of the widespread fear, lack of clear information and as a consequence of the movement restriction policies. These living conditions would be the cause for the deterioration of the mental and physical wellbeing for several participants.

In **Italy**, similarly to other countries such as Greece and Belgium, interviewees indicate that there are bureaucratic procedures and criteria that hinder the acquisition of valuable financial support from potential beneficiaries and citizens in need. In spite of the fact that several respondents indicated that they have indeed received financial support, they deem it to be insufficient and inconsistent, nevertheless appreciate the fact that had support. Moreover, interviewees in Italy appear to criticize the organization of the welfare state, increased prices on living expenses, hoarding of supplies and suggest that information provision has been adequate and on point such as in Belgium, and similarly to most target countries highlight the negative consequences that movement containment and social isolation had on the Italian society as well as the negative impact that the lack of social interaction had on both the general public and the vulnerable citizens. In relation to desired governmental support, Italian interviewees would prefer to experience a more organized and accountable governmental response who would present clear information and take into consideration vulnerable groups such as low SES citizens, the elderly and children whilst drafting policies and implementing crisis mitigation responses. In some cases, some interviewees appear to be content with the received support, nevertheless, the majority of citizens would prefer to see substantial support taking place which also includes the provision of adequate personal hygiene and protection equipment such as masks and disinfectant gels as well as the technological means for remote education. In addition, interviewees would also prefer to have support in relation to essential need items such as adequate food and water, which may not be able to acquire during the COVID-19 crisis.

In **Portugal**, regarding criticism in relation to governmental responses similarly to other target countries, the majority of interviewees highlight a lack of holistic support, albeit some interviewees indicate to have received financial governmental aid. In relation to desired support, interviewees indicate the need to have specialized medical personnel and social service employees assigned to vulnerable citizens for assistance in their daily activities, a more structured and encompassing welfare system, legal protection of employment which would secure a stable income and protect employees from working rights infringement (i.e. unlawful layoffs and compensation of working overtime). In addition, interviewees recommend that governmental responses should implement policies that would ensure the provision of support by distributing essential goods to citizens in need as well as allow pharmacies to deliver medication at home. In relation to recommendations towards decision makers and policy experts, citizens have underlined the importance of disseminating clear and on point information on health protocols via all means and methods (including telephone calls for citizens who

may have an impairment), situational awareness in relation to volunteering opportunities during crises, conduct vaccinations in health centers due to practical challenges such as the inability of travelling and establish local community markets for the socio-financially vulnerable citizens. Concluding, some interviewees suggested that increased policing is necessary in order that citizens abide by the hygiene protocols. In terms of vulnerability, similarly to other target countries, it is observed that pre-existing vulnerabilities were intensified and related mainly to socio-economic challenges. Interviewees indicate psychological and physical challenges emerged and were intensified during COVID-19 due to lack of sufficient support, as well as an unintended consequence of the implemented policies.

In **Spain**, governmental responses present weaknesses similarly to other target states governmental responses, which particularly relate to security the basic means of personal hygiene, rampant product and services price increase, insufficient governmental financial and psychological support in the cases that individuals received support and bureaucratic issues which act as hurdles for beneficiaries to receive assistance. Moreover, particularly young children, elderly, minorities and single parent families were similarly negatively impacted by both mitigation responses and COVID-19 isolation and containment measures. In addition, education and remote working, as well as securing employment during COVID-19 were challenged by the lack of adequate support and technological means to conduct the aforementioned activities. Overall, interviewees in Spain, similarly to the majority of other nations appear to criticize the governmental response efforts considering them to be insufficient and in certain cases counterproductive, with the exception of a few interviewees who consider these measures to be necessary. In relation to the desired support, interviewees in Spain would like to see a more encompassing welfare state that provides socio-economic and legal protection, particularly for undocumented citizens, citizens who were unemployed due to COVID-19, the elderly and children. Moreover, citizens have highlighted the importance of reinforcing public means of transportation, psychological support, the lack of a point of information that can be utilized to provide support for elderly that cannot access the internet or lack the technical skills as well as information transparency without overwhelming citizens.

Regarding governmental responses in **Sweden**, citizens indicate that social distance, isolation and human capacity in buildings protocols were difficult to follow and suggest that there was a lack of desired healthcare and public means of transportation frequency. Most interviewees suggest that COVID-19 and the policies had negative consequences in their psychological wellbeing particularly due to movement limitation. Another main finding is that, similarly to most countries, cases of hoarding would emerge resulting to shortages in essential need items such as food and toilet paper. In addition, the digitization of education and services became the new normality in Sweden similarly to other countries, which may some respondents took time to adjust in the new status quo. Emotional impact was also caused by COVID-19 policies in cases of relatives being hospitalized or passing away, to respondents who could not visit or participate in religious rituals as prior to COVID-19. Despite the negative consequences of isolation policies, Swedish interviewees appear to be positive on the implementation of local quarantines particularly for healthcare workers to avoid the spread of the disease, similarly to interviewees from other countries suggest that politicians should be held accountable for their policies, while also highlight that the mandatory wearing of face masks should have been enforced from the very start albeit can be challenging for children. Concluding, several interviewees suggest that COVID-19 and the way societies lived during COVID-19 can be interpreted as living during a war. In relation to desired support, Swedish interviewees appear to be divided in their

opinion, as some respondents are content with the way Sweden has managed COVID-19 and ensured a higher degree of individual liberties, while some others suggest that containment policies have been negative for children and adults, particularly in relation to social isolation. Swedish respondents also suggest that information dissemination has been carried out in a positive manner while they would desire a better level of healthcare and an increased degree of employment protection as many individuals have lost their employment due to COVID-19. In relation to vulnerability, similarly to all target countries, besides other groups, elderly citizens in Sweden have been mostly affected by COVID-19.

In **Wales**, respondents similarly to other target countries, criticized governmental responses particularly in relation to the implementation of confinement policies and the consequences they had on the mental wellbeing as well as practical socio-financial challenges, while trying to adapt to the new status quo. Several interviewees highlight a lack of governmental support particularly in essential need item provision. In relation to desired support, interviewees, similarly to the majority of the target states, highlighted the importance of clarity in information dissemination, a more cohesive welfare protection scheme particularly for the socio-financial stability of citizens as well as the protection of vulnerable individuals who did not have a sufficient support in relation to essential need items and psychological support. In terms of vulnerability, similarly to other countries, vulnerability reflects on healthcare, socio-financial challenges as well as cultural and legal obstacles many interviewees faced during the pandemic. Interviewees in several cases have compared the social and welfare structure between Wales and their country of origin, highlighting differences and insufficiencies in both cases. Overall, citizens in Wales highlight the need for a more encompassing system that takes care of the most vulnerable citizens during crises, similarly to the rest of the target countries.

5 Recommendations for decision makers, policy experts and relevant key stakeholders

In this section, the main key findings, lessons learned and recommendations will be presented:

5.1 Summary of key findings

- **Governmental Responses: impact, challenges, and critique:** Low SES citizens are struggling to make ends meet during COVID-19 due to the lack of accessible welfare policies. The welfare system during crises should be more comprehensive, as the absence of adequate governmental support can be a consequence of a long-standing social issue for single-parent families among low SES citizens. Non-pharmaceutical interventions such as movement restriction policies such as social isolation (lockdowns) and social distance measures may have a beneficial impact on the containment of the virus, nevertheless, they can have significantly negative impact on the economy of societies and wellbeing of low SES and vulnerable individuals if the implemented policies are prolonged, consecutive and a de-escalation – de-engagement strategy is absent. The negative impact stems from lack of social interaction, abrupt cease of employment as well as scarcity and/or unavailability of basic needs items and services.
- **Governmental Support: effective and ineffective measures:** A grassroots collection of opinions regarding desired support can yield valuable insights for policy development. Bureaucratic challenges can leave socio-economically vulnerable citizens stranded in times of need. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) can serve as an alternative approach to address systemic weaknesses.
- **Vulnerability:** Vulnerability is a complex issue magnified by COVID-19 and systemic deficiencies. The absence of welfare protocols may heighten the vulnerabilities of low SES citizens, while movement restriction policies can lead to unintended consequences such as deteriorating mental and physical health.

5.2 Lessons Learned

- Vulnerability is a multidimensional phenomenon encompassing socio-economic, health, legal, and cultural indicators. It has been exacerbated by COVID-19, systemic weaknesses, and inefficient policies, resulting in both expected and unexpected outcomes.
- Low SES citizens constitute a subset of the broader vulnerable population. In our target states they are often considered "societally translucent," meaning they are frequently neglected or unintentionally overlooked during policy implementation. This group faces vulnerability and well-being challenges in their daily lives, even before the onset of COVID-19, leading to a lingering feeling of abandonment by the state.
- The impact of COVID-19, policies, and implemented measures on low socio-economic citizens, albeit important, is predominantly viewed as ineffective, inefficient, and negative due to the absence of a comprehensive welfare strategy.

- Media and decision makers ought to be transparent, disregard the political cost while facing healthcare crises and adopt more human-centered approaches to combat pandemics. Decision makers should orientate the governmental responses with a post-pandemic perspective and financially assist businesses, vulnerable citizens and employees, reinforce the healthcare system, proceed with an open dialogue to identify lessons learned, mistakes and realistic improvement of responses for future crises as well as address the negative psychological impact that COVID-19 caused.
- Unregistered employment could increase the vulnerability of citizens due to not being entitled to financial benefits or labor exploitation of remote working basis employees.
- Facilitation of open dialogue between members of the society and decision makers, could be supported by municipality centers, schools, social media which could facilitate communication efforts such as awareness and information raising campaigns, in-person meetings with concerned citizens and formal method of documenting these concerns, empirical research utilizing questionnaires to minority groups and general public. These actions seem as feasible actions which would significantly engagement and communication between decision makers, general public and minority groups.
- In certain cases, it can be beneficial to have a more in-person approach to awareness raising campaigns even utilizing door-to-door campaigns, encourage the use of multi-polar, open dialogue discussion panels to examine a wide variety of topics and views as well as utilizing the re-direct method, which is a method that utilized targeted ads which can both inform social media end-users and more importantly, it can act as an effective method to actively combat disinformation.
- Authorities that implement policies such as, law enforcement agents, should tailor their approach towards low SES citizens and minority groups, adopting a politer and more humane character during complex healthcare crises while it is crucial that enforcing authorities acquire better education on social interactions and be provided with psychological support as they encounter several cases that would impact their mental health and well-being.
- Authorities and media should avoid labelling social groups (Such as the “youth” who are “irresponsible”) and instead should elaborate more on the usefulness and operating mechanisms of the vaccines as well as the potential side-effects in a clear and honest manner.
- The vaccination campaign, overall can be considered successful as well as the awareness raising campaigns that contributed in increasing vaccination rates due to explaining how beneficial a vaccine can be against COVID-19, nevertheless the pressure and widespread fear of being fined also contributed in the increased vaccination rate.

5.3 Recommendations

- Decision makers and policy experts are strongly advised to conduct a thorough re-evaluation of welfare policies and mitigation measures for health crises. This evaluation should take into account the unique characteristics of vulnerable groups, including low SES citizens, such as single-parent families etc. Stakeholders should develop more comprehensive welfare strategies and re-examine inclusion criteria for potential beneficiaries.

- Stakeholders should engage with communities through frequent initiatives and should disseminate relevant information in a clear and understandable manner to overcome educational challenges. Identifying that many low socio-economic status citizens (such as single-parent families, low income citizens etc) have limited available time, it is highly recommended that information should be tailored, concise, precise, and not subjected to frequent changes.
- Government mechanisms should consider the employment challenges faced by low SES citizens, particularly single parents, among other low SES citizens, who may be the sole providers for their families. They should provide substantial materialistic support in the form of benefits and essential items, as well as psychological support if employment is suspended. Moreover, a post-pandemic socio-economic strategy should include a re-introduction to employment plan. This could involve governmental mechanisms partially covering the monthly wages of beneficiaries and encouraging business owners to employ them, potentially through tax incentives.
- Stakeholders are encouraged to establish partnerships with strategic partners, such as NGOs, that played a significant role in supplementing governmental efforts during the pandemic. Collaboration between the public and private sectors can lead to more effective and efficient mitigation of socio-economic, health, legal, and cultural impacts during health crises.
- National legislative bodies, policy experts, and decision makers should examine and develop a legal framework to protect citizens during periods of widespread fear and crisis. Weaknesses in the current legal framework, such as respondents experiencing additional emotional stress due to financial uncertainty and landlord pressure, should be addressed. The government should implement welfare safety measures to ensure the survival of vulnerable citizens, especially regarding accommodation, healthcare, and the provision of essential items.
- Decision makers and policy experts should exercise caution when implementing movement restriction policies, such as curfews, due to their unforeseen negative consequences on the socio-economic status and physical and mental well-being of vulnerable citizens. Stakeholders should avoid prolonged curfews and instead develop de-escalation mechanisms to protect citizens while simultaneously limiting the spread of contagious viruses like COVID-19.
- It is recommended that actors who politicized and exploited the pandemic for personal gain, particularly by spreading falsified information should be held accountable. A post-pandemic perspective should be adopted to actively provide financial assistance for both vulnerable businesses, vulnerable citizens and employees, reinforcing the healthcare system, and facilitate open dialogue to identify lessons learned, mistakes and how to improve responses for future crises as well as address the negative psychological impact that COVID-19 caused.
- Governmental system mechanisms and relevant actors should develop protection mechanisms to address systemic gray areas and legislative weaknesses of the labor law, which fails to protect employees who work on a remote basis. It is important to protect employee's labor rights by abuses that involve reduction of the wages of remote working employees, increasing workload and disrespect of set work hours, which likely lead to reductions of productivity. Remote and on-site employee rights should be monitored by suitable governmental agencies to avoid a cascading phenomenon of employee rights violation, even after the pandemic.
- It is recommended that a well-structured, clear, feasible preparedness and response strategy and a post-pandemic action plan that takes into account weaknesses of marginalised groups in order

to mitigate the socio-economic consequences of the pandemic which were intensified pre-existing financial and social issues that posed a threat to their survival, is developed.

- During crises, policy and measure implementation authorities such as law enforcement agents can be considered societal role models, therefore law enforcement agents should exercise caution in handling complex situations, particularly if the implemented measures are interpreted as contradictory to their role. Law enforcement agents ought to be cautious and not demonstrate overzealousness during the implementation of non-pharmaceutical interventions (i.e. social isolation) as it may cause public discontent and can easily result in mismanagement. Law enforcement agents should be professionally respectful towards citizens who may not be aware of specific limitations and restrictions due to lack of clarity.
- Decision makers and policy experts are recommended to take into consideration lessons learned from the pandemic, particularly in relation to the negative consequences and actively work in reinforcing identified systemic weaknesses. These include the provision of welfare and support to businesses and individuals within the general population and in marginalised groups who may disregard implemented measures in order to secure their income during the pandemic.
- Stakeholders and communication experts are recommended to take into account the importance of conducting communication activities (i.e. debates) based on open dialogue and opinion multipolarity. The lack of multiple points of view on traditional media panels may have decreased their popularity among the general and minority populations.
- Communication campaigns should be clear and targeted, while also inclusive of specific socio-demographic groups, which may have been overlooked during COVID-19. Communication experts should employ a variety of means of communications during crises, whereas in relation to social media, could also employ the re-direct method which uses targeted ads which can both inform social media end-users and more importantly, it can act as an effective method to actively combat disinformation. In relation to vaccination, experts should communicate the usefulness of the vaccine for both the general population and vulnerable populations (i.e. cancer patients), their function and potential side-effects in a clear and transparent manner.
- Decision makers should actively work on constructing a common framework between stakeholders such as authorities, scientific community, embassies and administrative agencies at all governance levels, with emphasis on how to effectively communicate and implement measures relevant to the crisis at hand. Embassies should have a pivotal role in assisting foreign nationals, migrants and refugees, particularly allowing them to overcome language barriers.
- Pre-existing lack of trust and misinformation may negatively impact policy and measure implementation authorities (i.e. law enforcement agents). Decision makers should take into consideration weaknesses of the civil protection responses, particularly in high criminal activity areas and reinforce citizen protection which will subsequently mend trust issues. Authorities should provide proper training and education, particularly to improve the social interaction skills of authorities, as well as adequate wages that compensate the risks of their daily duties and responsibilities of deployed authorities (i.e. law enforcement agents).
- It is important to facilitate open dialogue between the wider social structure, low socio-economic citizens and the minority communities on bridging the gaps and identifying courses of action that

can be beneficial for minority communities, particularly in relation to their socio-economic and psychological wellbeing.

- Due to the financial challenges that contemporary societies of our target states face, decision makers are recommended to examine the erasure of the implemented fines which may cripple citizens and businesses.

6 Conclusion

Concluding on the results of the WP4, D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, authored by Spathi T., Bagkatzounis I., Arabatzi M., Tsekoura A., Papadaki D. and Eliezer, I. (2021), reveals based on the comparative analysis, that the majority of the abovementioned states have adhered to similar governmental modus operandi, in order to organize and lay out their COVID-19 strategy and responses. COVINFORM Stakeholders have taken into consideration measures and contributing factors, such as the socio-economic, legal, cultural characteristics of their States of origin, in order to tailor their approach, regarding governmental structure, vulnerable groups, and official channels of communication, through which accurate, timely and actionable information would be disseminated, which would also combat misinformation and address the needs of the society. Most of the researched states have opted in for a government-centred administrative approach, which allowed the issue of legislative frameworks, that provided enhanced legal and administrative powers, in contrast to the pre-COVID-19 pandemic era status quo. Furthermore, the researched States have adopted a holistic approach which included socio-economic, legal and cultural factors and challenges which surfaced alongside COVID-19.

In relation to D4.2 Research design: Governmental responses, authored by Spathi T., Bagkatzounis I., Tsekoura A., Papadaki D. and Eliezer, I. (2021) the COVINFORM consortium has developed the methodological background for the research activities, that will take place in the following deliverables, such as D4.3. In specific D4.2 elaborated further on how qualitative research and in particular targeted expert interviews would be conducted.

The D4.3 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment, authored by Bagkatzounis I., Tsekoura A., Marva A., and Eliezer, I. (2022), analysed and assessed different dimensions of government response to the COVID-19 pandemic in the EU and target countries, relying on both primary data collected through interviews with experts and stakeholders in specific research sites in the target countries, and secondary data. A part of the report focused on government planning and preparedness to COVID-19, while findings demonstrated that each target country followed its own response path, based on both pre-existing and newly developed strategies. The intensity and span of the pandemic was not the one expected by national governments, therefore, each country established a central authority in charge and new bodies, task forces or working groups that included often public health experts to provide advice for policy and decision-making. Nevertheless, final decisions have been taken under the responsibility of the central governments of the States and often caused confusion amongst both the population and actors involved in pandemic management. Another part focused on governmental approaches in defining and addressing vulnerability to COVID-19. Governments in the target countries have identified vulnerabilities based on different variables related to e.g., health, cultural, economic, and social factors. Those perceived to be more vulnerable were elderly people, people who did not speak the national language, migrants and asylum seekers, single-parent families, or workers in certain types of businesses. However, the definition of vulnerability changed with the time, when governments realized that young and healthy groups, also experienced vulnerability. With approaches to vulnerability been diversified, some countries mainly defined and targeted vulnerable groups by providing financial, psychological, or housing support, while others did not employ a tailored approach. The findings revealed that vulnerability is a condition that varies across individuals and groups based on their sociodemographic characteristics. An additional part focused on responses on multiple levels of governance, governmental structures and on how European

communities strive to tailor their responses based on contributing factors and unique or shared characteristics among the European countries, while another focuses on the state backed economic and social measures, with findings highlighting the different measures implemented in the EU and in target countries to cope with the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic on economic wellbeing of people and organizations. The target countries have established economic instruments to support and protect businesses, including funds for businesses and vulnerable groups as well as funds for the pandemic recovery and have also developed and implemented social welfare measures for vulnerable groups. A final part focused on the socio-political, ethical, and legal factors influencing government preparedness and response in the target countries, with the findings reporting the ethical and legal challenges existing with the implementation of restrictive measures, the surveillance and contact tracing responses, as well as the COVID-19 alert and warning systems, since these measures run the risk of creating discrimination between people or creating distrust among citizens, as well as of restricting human and privacy rights.

The D4.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts, authored by Bagkatzounis I., Marva A., and Tsekoura Anna (2022), provided a summary and an interpretation of the findings of D4.1 – D4.3 from an interdisciplinary and intersectional standpoint, within the theoretical framework established in WP2 and WP3 respectively, by providing a synthesis of governmental responses and impact and on lessons learnt on two different time periods based on empirical research. The overall empirical research and research findings have highlighted several limitations, research gaps and topics that could be academically examined and explored even further. The report goes forward to propose five Policy recommendations: 1) Containment policies (lockdown, border closure, curfews...) i.e., non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) may have several unintended consequences, 2) Suspension of the economic activities: catering, hospitality, and touristic sector, with increased support and utmost protection for workers at the facilities that remained open, so that these key workers can continue their work. 3) Adaptation of education during the crisis: suspension and online teaching. 4) Compulsory wearing of facemasks. 5) Economic activities and labour markets in the pandemic, with state policies that can be heralded as helpful in the protection of vulnerable people, specifically including wage replacement for people with a low socio-economic status without demanding change to their job or forcing them to take up jobs that would more expose them to the virus.

D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, authored by Bagkatzounis I., Marva A., Dima E., and Tsekoura Anna (2022) gave information based on a comprehensive comparative analysis across countries, and noted that even though in some cases there have been no structural governmental changes since the beginning of the pandemic, in many if not the most targeted countries a series of governmental and crisis management mechanism structural reforms were observed as of April 1st, 2021 until late May 2022. The extend of these reforms differed, from changes of key decision makers even of the highest level, to changes of persons in key ministries due to internal political friction or as an attempt to introduce new political figures through inner-party rotation. In any case, the government-centered administrative approach and the modus operandi in pandemic management, adopted by the vast majority of the countries during the previous pandemic phases were largely maintained. The legislative initiatives that provided enhanced legal and administrative powers to governmental entities were extended further even though some measures raised issues of constitutionality. At the same time, almost all researched countries endorsed strategies aiming to strike a better balance between the implementation of public health measures and the continuity of

economic and social activities, that had been suspended during the pandemic. Regarding risk perception, even though there are not currently sufficient data covering all the targeted countries and more research is needed upon this matter, relevant studies carried out in a number of partner countries, reveal that because people perceive the pandemic as a serious matter, abide with the implemented measures adopting preventive behaviours, like hand hygiene, facemask wearing and social distancing. When COVID 19 vaccines were finally made available, all partner countries developed and adopted strategic plans for the disposition of vaccination campaigns at a national level. Either pre-existing or ad hoc governmental authorities established during the pandemic, were charged with the task of supervising and coordinating the respective procedures. In this context, vaccination target groups were adopted categorizing citizens into different priority groups, based on age, vulnerability, pre-existing medical conditions, risk exposure or other profession-based criteria.

The D4.6 Research design: Governmental responses - update M26, authored by Bagkatzounis I., Dima E., Tsekoura A. and Ioannis Konstantopoulos (2022), draw from the main lessons learned of the research design for the activities within WP4, that the partners can and are advised to examine governmental responses and their impacts, initially from a holistic perspective with a broader scope at an EU, national, regional and local level. The report recommends, that partners should narrow down the research scope to more targeted research questions in accordance with the latest developments and research gaps, as research progresses, in order to avoid unnecessary repetition. The main difficulties of designing and carrying out research was the unavoidable highly dynamic and ever-changing landscape of policy and decision making upon facing the unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic, and relevant recruitment challenges, due to the fact that decision and policy makers at a national level have severely limited availability to participate in the empirical research (interviews).

The D4.7 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment – update M32, authored by Zainab M., Niamh A., and Su Anson with contributions from Bagkatzounis I., Dima E., Tsekoura A. and Ioannis Konstantopoulos (2023), presented an update of the different dimensions of government response to the COVID-19 pandemic across all the COVINFORM countries. The report extracted information from the previous deliverables D4.1 and D4.5, as well as expert interviews conducted with experts and stakeholders up until May 2023. The report also highlighted similarities in terms of pandemic preparedness and planning, vulnerabilities identified, COVID-19 responses, economic and social welfare responses, and socio-political, legal, and ethical factors that played a role in government preparedness and response. All the dimensions touched upon, covered three different periods of the pandemic and they are: 1) pre-COVID-19/T0, 2) the start of COVID-19 up until vaccination/T1, and 3) the emergence of the Omicron variant and onwards/T2. Some key findings relating to the dimensions covered include the following: 1) Different periods of the pandemic (i.e., T0, T1, and T2) saw changes in terms of which groups in society were considered to be vulnerable, 2) most under study countries did see the evolution of their crisis response as the COVID-19 pandemic progressed and 3) The economic measures introduced were crucial in helping those severely impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic financially.

The D4.8 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts - update M33, Bagkatzounis I., Dima E., Tsekoura A. and Ioannis Konstantopoulos (2023), identified and examined good practices and lessons learned that stemmed from the aforementioned governmental responses, while generating tailored recommendations for policy and decision makers. The report conducted an overview of policies and practices developed and implemented in relation to the socio-political structure and governmental response, alterations in COVID-19 related measures and policies, as well

as the interpretation of vulnerability from each target state. It was revealed that some COVINFORM states have a fragmented administrative socio-political structure, which despite having entities of executive authority, regional and local governments and communities, enjoy great autonomy. Nevertheless, the national government had the main role in decision and policy making. The report acknowledged the several good practices during the First Pandemic Phase (T0), Second Pandemic Phase (T1) and Third Pandemic Phase (T2), making recommendations, while it agreed that in relation to vulnerability, most if not all target states, did not adopt an encompassing interpretation which predominantly focused on health considerations, something which later changed.

Moreover, within the context of WP4, with the exception of the aforementioned deliverables in relation to governmental responses the following outputs have been produced:

Blogposts

- Bagkatzounis, I., Konstantopoulos I. (2023). Policy and practice mismatches in governmental responses during the COVID-19 pandemic. Available at: <https://www.covinform.eu/2023/07/26/policy-and-practice-mismatches-in-governmental-responses-during-the-covid-19-pandemic/>.
- Bagkatzounis I., Marva A., Eliezer I. & Spathi T. (2021). Government and the pandemic: structures and response. Available at: <https://www.covinform.eu/2021/08/18/government-and-the-pandemic/>.

Bi-monthly reports

- Spathi, T., Bagkatzounis, I., Arabatzi, M., Tsekoura, A., Papadaki, D., and Eliezer, I. (2021). COVID-19: Findings on the Governmental Responses in COVINFORM countries. Bi-monthly report 4, July 2021. COVINFORM H2020 Project No. 101016247. Available at: <https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2021/07/COVINFORM-Brochure-A4-Bi-Monthly-Report-4-1.0.pdf>.

Policy Briefs

- Bagkatzounis, I., Konstantopoulos I. and Tsekoura, A. (2023). The impact of COVID-19 on marginalized groups in Greece. Available at: <https://www.covinform.eu/>.
- Bagkatzounis, I., Konstantopoulos I. and Tsekoura, A. (2023). COVID-19 Governmental responses and challenges The case study of low socio-economic status citizens in Greece. Available at: <https://www.covinform.eu/>.
- Bagkatzounis, I., Konstantopoulos I. and Tsekoura, A. (2023). Policing during COVID-19 The impact of Coronavirus on Law Enforcement Agents. Available at: <https://www.covinform.eu/>.

Concluding, D8.3 actively engaged in the analysis and cross-country comparison of data that relate to critically reviewing preparedness pandemic plans based on WP4 deliverables and relevant qualitative and quantitative research conducted within the context of the COVINFORM project. Moreover, based on the analysis of data, a generation, development and synthesis of main findings, lessons learned and recommendations has been presented in relation to protocols and principles for decision-makers taking the lead in implementing pandemic measures. Decision makers, policy experts and relevant key stakeholders can draw valuable insights which will significantly increase the effectiveness and efficiency rate of their tailored governmental mechanism responses for the potential future crises.

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Bagkatzounis, I., Konstantopoulos I. and Tsekoura, A. (2023). Policing during COVID-19 The impact of Coronavirus on Law Enforcement Agents. Available at: <https://www.covinform.eu/>.

Websites

<https://www.covinform.eu/>.

WP4 Deliverables

Available for download at <https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/technical-reports/>

D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses

D4.2 Research design: Governmental responses

D4.3 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment

D4.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts

D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22

D4.6 Research design: Governmental responses– update M26

D4.7 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment– update M32

D4.8 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts– update M33

WP5 Deliverables

D5.7 Analysis: Public health responses and impact - update M33